

Conference report – The influence of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on agricultural activity, food and energy security, and environmental degradation¹

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Abstract

The aim of the international online conference in the hybrid form “The influence of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on agricultural activity, food and energy security and environmental degradation” was, firstly, to indicate the impact of Russia's invasion of Ukraine on agricultural activity, food security, energy security and environmental degradation, including economic issues; secondly, the assessment of how the legal regulations on the abovementioned issues respond to the problems and challenges related to the war in Ukraine in the national, European and global aspects.

29 speakers took part in the conference, representing 25 academic centres, and government and non-government organizations from 8 countries. The issues raised in the presentations during the conference were part of the global debate on food security and energy security in the EU and in the whole world in the context of the war in Ukraine.

Speakers discussed proposals to improve food security and energy independence (including the use of renewable energy sources) in Ukraine, Poland and the EU in the current context. The presentations also included legal and economic analyses of the impact of military operations on the environment in Ukraine, including soils.

Conference report

The international conference in a hybrid form, i.e. on-line on the MS Teams platform and at the Faculty of Law and Administration of the Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poland, took place on March 23-24, 2023. As many of the conference participants were from Ukraine, a country at war, the conference was mainly in the form of a virtual meeting. All sessions were held in English.

¹ The Conference was held within the framework of projects number 055 “IDUB Support for Researches from Ukraine” and number 068 “IDUB Support for Researches from Ukraine” implemented by A.Bilochenko, scholar at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, from June 2022 to April 2023. The Scientific Supervisor of those projects was Prof. UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń (Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Protection Law).

The conference was organized by Prof. UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń (Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Protection Law), Poznan, Poland, and Dr Andrii Bilochenko, UAM postdoctoral researcher (National Science Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics" in Kyiv, Ukraine), with the support of the Adam Mickiewicz University's management and the Faculty of Law and Administration of UAM.

The conference was officially opened by AMU prof. Dr hab. Tomasz Nieborak, Dean of the Faculty of Law and Administration of UAM. The conference participants were also read a letter from Janusz Wojciechowski, the Commissioner of European Union for Agriculture. Opening speeches were also delivered by: Professor Leonardo Pastorino, University of Verona, Italy, President of UMAU (World Union of Agricultural Law and Food Law) and Professor Dr. iur. Dr. h.c. Roland Norer, University of Luzerne, CEDR (European Council for Rural Law).

The aim of the conference was to indicate the impact of Russia's invasion of Ukraine on agricultural activity, food security, energy security and environmental degradation, including economic issues. In addition, the organizers of the conference aimed to assess how the legal regulation of these issues responds to the problems and challenges associated with the war in Ukraine from the national, European and global perspectives.

The conference was held over two days. The first day was divided into three parts – three sessions. The first of them was devoted mainly to the issues of agricultural activity, agricultural land use, and support for the agriculture of Ukraine under the conditions of martial law. The first part of the conference was opened by Dr Olaf Heidelbach, Economic and Policy Analyst in DG AGRI, (DGAGRI, European Commission), Brussels, Belgium, with the presentation "European Union aid for Ukraine. The impact of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on European agriculture and food Policy"

Then Dr Andrii Bilochenko, research scholar at Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland presented his thoughts on the subject – "Legal and economic principles of agricultural activity and food supply chains during the war in Ukraine". The speaker paid special attention to the problematic issues of logistics in Ukraine in the conditions of war.

Subsequently, Professor Volodymyr Nosik, National University of Kyiv, Member of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine introduced the topic – "Legal and institutional problems associated with agricultural land use in the de-occupied territories of Ukraine". Professor Volodymyr Kovaliv, Dean, Lviv National Environmental University, Ukraine, presented the topic "Changes in the financial potential of agriculture in Ukraine during the war". Dr Kobayrenko Yulia, Institute for Sustainable Agriculture, Spain (CSIC) addressed the audience with the issue of "The agricultural sector of Ukraine during one year of war".

The second session covered issues associated with financial support for agriculture and food security. Professor Oleksandra Mandych, State Biotechnological University (Kharkiv, Ukraine), regional coordinator of the Young Scientists Council at the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine presented a report on the topic "Financial changes for strategic management systems of agricultural companies in the conditions of war and post-war reconstruction".

Then Dr Nadiia Stoliarchuk (Senior Researcher of the Department of Organization of Scientific Research and Innovative Development of the National Scientific Centre "Institute of Agrarian Economics", Kyiv, Ukraine) addressed the topic "The influence of Russian aggression on the introduction of

innovations in the agricultural sector of the economy”. Dr Hanna Bazhenova, Institute of Central Europe, Lublin, Poland presented her assessment of “Ukraine’s agricultural sector after one year of war: old and new challenges”.

Professor UAM dr hab. Aneta Suchoń, Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Law, Faculty of Law and Administration, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland addressed the audience with the paper “The impact of Russia's invasion of Ukraine on the Polish agri-food law, agricultural activity and food processing”.

Professor Dr hab. Olena Hafurova, Professor of Agrarian, Land and Environmental Law Department, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, and Professor Dr hab. Volodymyr Yermolenko, Corresponding Member of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine, Head of Agrarian, Land and Environmental Law Department, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine (Kyiv, Ukraine) presented a joint paper on the topic: “Food security of Ukraine in war conditions: problems of legal regulation”.

The third session of the Conference was mainly devoted to the issues associated with food security, especially supply chains and environmental safety in different countries of the EU and the world. Professor María Esther Muñoz Espada, Professor of Civil Law, Faculty of Law, Spain, expressed her vision on the topic: “Legal measures to secure the food supply chain”. Professor Dr hab. Mariusz Maciejczak, SGGW, Poland and Dr Julia Galchynska, NULES, Ukraine presented the results of their joint research on the topic: “The domino effect in the food supply chain of Ukraine – challenges for food security, competitiveness, and prospective post-war reconstruction”. Professor Doctor of Law Tetiana Kurman, Head of the Department of Land and Agrarian Law and Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University, Kharkiv, Ukraine presented a report on the topic “Food and agro-ecological security of Ukraine and the world in the conditions of armed conflict: problems of legal support”.

Professor Mihály Kurucz, Faculty of Law and Political Sciences, Eötvös Lorand University, Budapest, Department for Agrarian Law, Hungary spoke at the conference on the topic: “Tensions of security of European agroproducers and food safety in Eastern European countries of the EU facing to the solidarity lanes initiatives to support the agri-food cereals export of Ukraine”. Dr Tarek Ben Hassen (Qatar University, Doha), answered the following question – “Impacts of the Russia-Ukraine War on global food security: a crisis multiplier?” The first panel was closed by the presentation of Professor Antonios Maniatis, Assistant Professor at the Merchant Navy Academy of Aspropyrgos, Athens, Greece, on the topic “Impacts of the war in Ukraine on the rights to food and energy”.

The second day of the Conference was opened by Professor of environmental law Shinichi Okuda, Takushoku University, Tokyo, Japan, whose report was dedicated to the issue of “Legal and policy challenges regarding sustainable agriculture and energy in Japan”. Then Dr Maria Dehtarienko spoke (Department of Agricultural Law and Land Management, Faculty of Law, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University, Lublin, Poland). Her topic was “International determinants of food security”. An interesting and comprehensive view of the problem of the legal basis for the assessment of damages and losses caused by the armed aggression to land and soil resources: methodology, analysis, directions for improvement assessment of damages and losses because of war was presented in a report by Prof. Dr hab. Anatolii Kucher (Department of Management of Organizations Lviv Polytechnic National University; Chief Researcher, National Scientific Center “Institute for Soil Science and Agrochemistry Research named after O.N. Sokolovsky”, Ukraine). Professor Dr of Law Kovalenko Tetiana (Department

of Land and Agrarian Law, Educational and Scientific Law School, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine) gave a presentation on the topic “Lands of Ukraine as an object of ecocide in the - Russia-Ukraine War”.

The Director of International Affairs Department, Ministry of Climate and Environment, Poland – Marcin Białek – also gave a presentation on topic “The Polish energy sector after Russia's military aggression against Ukraine”.

Subsequently, Dr Anna Pastukh, Lawyer of the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine presented the subject: “The energy sector in Ukraine during the war: an answer of bioenergy sector”. Professor dr hab. Heorhiy Cherevko (Lviv National Environmental University, Ukraine) addressed the audience with the paper – “Russia's military aggression as a challenge for the environment of Ukraine”. Dr Oksana Borodina (Institute of Industrial Economics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine) presented the subject “Energy, industrial and fiscal innovations as the basic instruments of the economic framework of post-war Ukraine”. Mgr Tomasz Marzec, PhD Candidate (Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Law, Faculty of Law and Administration, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland) presented a report on topic: “Community energy: a sustainable path for energy security in Europe”.

A rather interesting and alternative approach to the development of international transport corridors was presented in the report by MA in Law Marina Myklush (Lawyer, CEO of the Law firm “FOX” of Marina Myklysh). Her topic was: “Interstate Transit Corporation (perspectives)”.

In conclusion – 29 speakers took part in the conference, which represented 25 academic centres, government and non-government organizations from 8 countries. The issues raised in the presentations during the conference were part of the global debate on food security and energy security in the EU and the whole world in the context of the war in Ukraine. Speakers discussed proposals to improve food security and energy independence (including the use of renewable energy sources) in Ukraine, Poland and the EU in the current context. The presentations also included legal and economic analyses of the impact of military operations on the environment in Ukraine, including soils.